

DIDACTIC REQUIREMENTS FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION RESIDENCES

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Just as theories form the basis of each field, the methodology of traditional and online teaching of English is also carried out based on certain theories. Before talking about the theories used in the field of methodology, let us dwell on the definitions given to the word theory by scientists and its significance. According to J. Ddonahiu, the theory is a set of principles based on the result of observations made in this laboratory. In order to study a particular subject in depth, it is definitely advisable to study the theories that form the basis of this science. J.Wakker argues that the study of theories is considered crucial to the real-life application of learned knowledge . The methodology of teaching a foreign language is carried out based on the theories of “education (learning)” in terms of linguistics and Language Teaching. An in-depth study of these theories makes it possible to understand how the process of traditional and online learning of a foreign language occurs. The principles of this theory are used as a guide in the selection of strategies and techniques in ensuring the teaching of a foreign language.

One such theory is the theory of Constructivism, which promotes the idea of independent study of a foreign language. This theory serves as the basis for personality-oriented methods, and its most important feature is that when a foreign language is taught on the basis of the theory of Constructivism, the role of the teacher in the educational process is limited to guidance, and not a source of knowledge that answers all questions.

S.Chuang acknowledges that the theory of Constructivism is scientifically discussed in three different ways: a) individual constructivism; b) social constructivism; C) contextualism. In Individual constructivism, knowledge is built and studied precisely from the experience of an individual. That is, learning is seen as an internal cognitive activity. Jerome Bruner is the founder of individual constructivism, which argues that rather than the teacher explaining all the information, students themselves can effectively remember this information for a long time, having a deep understanding of it if they learn it through exercises. P.According to ertmer, when a student learns new knowledge through experience (feeling and experiencing), they also develop creativity and

problem-solving skills, stimulating active participation in the learning process with high motivation, autonomy and responsibility.

Rather, social constructivism does not represent an individual's experiential learning, but rather that different perspectives are discussed in the educational process and new knowledge is acquired during collaborative work. S.Zhuang argues that the educational process is a fundamental principle of social constructivism, in which knowledge is built through social interaction, working in collaboration with others, discussing among themselves. The theory of social constructivism was founded by the Russian scientist Lev Vygotsky, in whose opinion the learners understand the information better by discussing it through mutual interaction. L.Vygotsky enters into the theory of social constructivism the category of "another more knowledgeable", that is, when the learner comes into contact with "another more knowledgeable", social interaction occurs positively. The "other more knowledgeable" can be a teacher, an instructor, an older or younger person, a peer, and even computers.

L.Another important term in Vygotsky's theory is the "proximal development space", which is the distance between the level of current knowledge and the level of potential development resulting from social interaction with other people. L.Vygotsky represents the area of proximal development.

In the case of the contextualism type of Constructivism theory, however, education is considered to be conducted in connection with an authentic context and an authentic assessment. The use of authentic materials in teaching English allows the student to be able to apply acquired knowledge outside the classroom. In a word, constructivism theory considers teaching with authentic materials effective by engaging in interactionism, organizing autonomous education with personality-oriented methods.

A.According to Gray, proponents of Constructivism theory believe that when a teacher explains on the basis of a teacher-oriented approach, the student effectively calculates not a lesson that sits quietly and listens, but a lesson in which a new topic is actively mastered by students, treating the student as the founder, creator of his cognitive activity.

T.M.Daffy and D.X.Jonassen also believes that learner knowledge in constructivism theory is built independently by the learner. Constructivism theory supports a person-oriented approach, that is, in a foreign language lesson, the student practically (assuming, predicting, discussing, and doing an exercise), not on the basis of theory.

The Chinese scientist Ping Wan, however, explains this theory more clearly: students build their knowledge by actively participating in the educational process, working cooperatively, establishing autonomous education and taking a creative approach by L.V.Kupal also found in his research work that with teaching on the basis of the theory of Constructivism, it is possible to independently make decisions, synthesize and independently understand the content and actively develop problem-solving skills in the educational process⁴. The theory of Constructivism emphasizes learning more than teaching, stimulating the student's independent work and personal participation in all stages of the lesson. The fact that many researchers and teachers actively use constructivist principles in creating a new educational environment indicates the importance of the role of this theory in the effective organization of the educational process.

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